

Syllabus Computational bioengineering

1. Introduction

The learning goals indicate the requirements of each lecture of the course 'Computational bioengineering' of 6 ECTS. Based on these requirements the instructors can format their lecture based on their own teaching preferences, knowledge and experience, while ensuring a qualitative course. Note that some learning goals are formulated for more than one lecture. This does not mean that the learning goals should be achieved in each of these lectures. It is the aim that the learning goals are achieved in at least one of the lectures, but how they are distributed over the lectures is up to the preferences of the instructor.

2. Overview lectures and exercise sessions

Week	Lecture	Topic lecture	Exercise session	Topic exercise session
1	L01	Recalls of human pathophysiology	P01	Recalls of human pathophysiology
2	L02	Recalls of biophysics	P02	Recalls of biophysics
3	L03	Recalls of biochemistry	P03	Recalls of biochemistry
4	L04	Recalls of numerical analysis	P04	Recalls of numerical analysis
5	L05	Stochastic modeling	P05	Stochastic modeling
6	L06	Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part I	P06	Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part I
7	L07	Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part II	P07	Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part II
8	L08	Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part I	P08	Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part I
9	L09	Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part II	P09	Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part II
10	L10	Development of an in silico trials solution	P10	Development of an in silico trials solution
11	L11	Credibility of predictive models part I	P11	Credibility of predictive models part I
12	L12	Credibility of predictive model part II	P12	Credibility of predictive model part II

3. Lectures

L01: Recalls of human pathophysiology

Applicable ILOs

H1.3.1: Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding human pathophysiology

Learning goals

- *Explain the pathophysiology for common diseases in the human body.*
- *Translate given pathophysiological processes into mathematical models;*
- *Illustrate how pathophysiological processes can be represented in computational models with two examples.*

L02: Recalls of biophysics

Applicable ILOs

H1.3.2: Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology

Learning goals

- *Explain well-known biophysical processes of the human body and their relation to human pathophysiology;*
- *Translate given biophysical processes into mathematical models;*
- *Illustrate how biophysical processes can be represented in computational models with two examples.*

L03: Recalls of biochemistry

Applicable ILOs

H1.3.2: Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology

Learning goals

- *Explain well-known biochemical processes of the human body and their relation to human pathophysiology;*
- *Translate given biochemical processes into mathematical models;*
- *Illustrate how biochemical processes can be represented in computational models with two examples.*

L04: Recalls of numerical analysis

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Select appropriate algorithms to numerically solve a set of linear and a set of non-linear equations;*
- *Select appropriate algorithms to solve an optimisation problem;*
- *Select appropriate strategies to calculate derivatives and integrals of given functions;*
- *Select appropriate strategies to approximate a given function based on polynomials and splines;*
- *Explain the underlying principles of computational modeling techniques such as finite element analysis and computational fluid dynamics.*

L05: Stochastic modeling

Applicable ILOs

H5.4.6: Understand the capabilities and the requirements of stochastic models

Learning goals

- *Showcase the use of stochastic modeling in healthcare based on two example cases;*
- *Describe the characteristics of stochastic modeling;*
- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of stochastic modeling in in silico medicine.*

L06: Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part I

Applicable ILOs

H5: Develop in silico methodologies

H5.4.7: Understand the capabilities and requirements of optimisation models

H5.6: Develop a knowledge-driven model

H5.6.3: Formulate the model in terms of idealisations

H5.6.11: Conduct initial validation to confirm the model's design choices

Learning goals

- *Explain when an in silico model is referred to as knowledge-driven;*
- *Elucidate the different steps of the workflow to develop a knowledge-driven in silico model;*
- *Give two examples of state-of-the-art knowledge-driven in silico models in healthcare*
- *Describe the benefits and drawbacks of a knowledge-driven in silico model in healthcare;*
- *Identify the model design choices and how these choices can be validated.*

L07: Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part II

Applicable ILOs

H5: Develop in silico methodologies

H5.4.7: Understand the capabilities and requirements of optimisation models

H5.6: Develop a knowledge-driven model

H5.6.3: Formulate the model in terms of idealisations

H5.6.11: Conduct initial validation to confirm the model's design choices

Learning goals

- *Explain when an in silico model is referred to as knowledge-driven;*
- *Elucidate the different steps of the workflow to develop a knowledge-driven in silico model;*
- *Give two examples of state-of-the-art knowledge-driven in silico models in healthcare;*
- *Describe the benefits and drawbacks of a knowledge-driven in silico model in healthcare;*
- *Identify the model design choices and how these choices can be validated.*

L08: Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part I

Applicable ILOs

H5: Develop in silico methodologies

H5.4.1: Understand the capabilities and the requirements of machine learning models

H5.4.6: Understand the capabilities and the requirements of stochastic models

H5.5: Develop a data-driven model

H5.5.1: Collect and properly organise data

H5.5.2: Curate data

H5.5.4: Train the model

H5.5.5: Evaluate and tune the model on the training set

H5.5.6: Validate the model on test sets

Learning goals

- *Explain when an in silico model is referred to as data-driven;*
- *Elucidate the different steps of the workflow to develop a data-driven in silico model;*
- *Give two examples of state-of-the-art data-driven in silico models in healthcare;*
- *Formulate the characteristics of a machine learning model;*
- *Formulate the characteristics of a stochastic model;*
- *Describe the benefits and drawbacks of a data-driven in silico model in healthcare;*
- *Compare the benefits and drawbacks of a data-driven in silico model in healthcare to those of a knowledge-driven model.*

L09: Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part II

Applicable ILOs

H5: Develop in silico methodologies

H5.4.1: Understand the capabilities and the requirements of machine learning models

H5.4.6: Understand the capabilities and the requirements of stochastic models

H5.5: Develop a data-driven model

H5.5.1: Collect and properly organise data

H5.5.2: Curate data

H5.5.4: Train the model

H5.5.5: Evaluate and tune the model on the training set

H5.5.6: Validate the model on test sets

Learning goals

- *Explain when an in silico model is referred to as data-driven;*
- *Elucidate the different steps of the workflow to develop a data-driven in silico model;*
- *Give two examples of state-of-the-art data-driven in silico models in healthcare;*
- *Formulate the characteristics of a machine learning model;*
- *Formulate the characteristics of a stochastic model;*
- *Describe the benefits and drawbacks of a data-driven in silico model in healthcare;*
- *Compare the benefits and drawbacks of a data-driven in silico model in healthcare to those of a knowledge-driven model.*

L10: Development of an in silico trials solution

Remark: While the students might benefit from the refreshment of some concepts, collaboration with the course 'introduction to in silico medicine' is recommended to avoid overlap.

Applicable ILOs

H5: Develop in silico methodologies

Learning goals

- *Identify the different steps required to develop an in silico trial based on a data-driven or knowledge-driven model;*
- *Apply the different steps required to develop an in silico trial based on a knowledge-driven model for a given example case;*
- *Apply the different steps required to develop an in silico trial based on a data-driven model for a given example case;*

L11: Credibility of predictive models part I

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Illustrate the importance of a credibility assessment in in silico medicine based on two state-of-the-art examples;*
- *Identify the common sources of errors in the development of in silico models;*
- *Distinguish between uncertainty and variability;*
- *Explain the meaning and relevance of verification, validation and uncertainty quantification in in silico modeling;*
- *Formulate a definition of the terms question of interest and context of use in the framework of in silico modeling;*
- *Clarify the subsequent steps of the credibility workflow, proposed in the ASME V&V40 guidelines related to in silico modeling;*
- *Apply the subsequent steps of the credibility workflow, proposed in the ASME V&V40 guidelines related to in silico modeling, to a given example case.*

L12: Credibility of predictive model part II

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Illustrate the importance of a credibility assessment in in silico medicine based on two state-of-the-art examples;*
- *Identify the common sources of errors in the development of in silico models;*
- *Distinguish between uncertainty and variability;*
- *Explain the meaning and relevance of verification, validation and uncertainty quantification in in silico modeling;*
- *Formulate a definition of the terms question of interest and context of use in the framework of in silico modeling;*
- *Clarify the subsequent steps of the credibility workflow, proposed in the ASME V&V40 guidelines related to in silico modeling;*
- *Apply the subsequent steps of the credibility workflow, proposed in the ASME V&V40 guidelines related to in silico modeling, to a given example case.*

4. Exercise sessions

The learning goals indicated in grey correspond to learning goals that have also been formulated for the lectures. By pursuing the same learning goal in a different context (e.g. understanding an example during the lecture and applying a concept during the exercise session), a better understanding of the considered aspect is expected.

P01: Recalls of human pathophysiology

Description

The students receive an example case on a human disease. Based on the content of the lecture, they should be aware of the underlying pathophysiological processes. The students translate these pathophysiological processes into a mathematical model.

Learning goals

- *Identify the underlying pathophysiological process for a given example case of a human disease;*
- *Translate given pathophysiological processes into mathematical models.*

P02: Recalls of biophysics

Description

The students receive an example case on a human disease. Based on the content of the lecture, they should be to identify the biophysical processes. The students translate these biophysical processes into a mathematical model. The mathematical model can, for example, be used to compare a diseased subject to a healthy subject.

Learning goals

- *Identify the underlying biophysical process for a given example case of a human disease;*
- *Translate given biophysical processes into mathematical models;*

P03: Recalls of biochemistry

Description

The students receive an example case on a human disease. Based on the content of the lecture, they should be to identify the biochemical processes. The students translate these biochemical processes into a mathematical model. The mathematical model can, for example, be used to compare a diseased subject to a healthy subject.

Learning goals

- Identify the underlying biochemical processes for a given example case of a human disease;
- Translate given biochemical processes into mathematical models;

P04: Recalls of numerical analysis

Description

The students select (multiple) appropriate algorithms for the given assignment and compare their results, e.g. forward vs. backward difference, multiple optimisation algorithms. The students perform a simple finite element (FE) or computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis, by manually implementing the equations in a python/matlab script.

Learning goals

- Select appropriate numerical algorithms to solve the provided assignment by choosing from the algorithms considered during the course;
- Critically analyse the impact of the applied numerical algorithms;
- Implement the required equations to perform a simple finite element or computational fluid dynamics analysis.

P05: Stochastic modeling

Description

The students receive a data set and fit a proper distribution on the given data. The students sample this fitted distribution of the input data. Here, the students get acquainted with different sampling algorithms, by applying them to a given input distribution. Based on a given model, the students obtain the distribution of the output data. In order to critically interpret the output data, it is important to consider the impact of the input distribution and sampling on the output distribution. Eventually, the students draw conclusions based on the obtained results.

Learning goals

- Select appropriate sampling algorithms on a given set of input data;
- Implement appropriate sampling algorithms on a given set of input data;
- Analyse the impact of the sampling of the input distribution on the output distribution;

P06: Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part I

Description

The students get acquainted with finite element (FE) or computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, by making one or more simple, standard models in commercial or well-developed software (e.g. Abaqus or FEBio for FE). Afterwards, the students receive an example pathophysiological case where the underlying mechanism of the disease is defined. The students then translate the given information

into an appropriate simplified geometry, material behaviour and suitable boundary and loading conditions.

Learning goals

- *Use existing FE or CFD software to create a simple computational model;*
- *Define an appropriate geometry and material behaviour and suitable boundary and loading conditions for a given pathological example case with a known underlying mechanism.*

P07: Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part II

Description

The student create a mesh for the determined geometry (part I) and implement the their model in FE or CFD software. While keeping the model sufficiently simple to avoid convergence issues at this stage, the students should pay attention to the interpretation of the result and the impact of the choices they made in the development of their model (part I).

Learning goals

- *Use FE or CFD software to create a simple computational model for a given pathophysiological case;*
- *Critically discuss the obtained model output and the impact of the modelling assumptions.*

P08: Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part I

Description

The get acquainted with the basics of machine learning algorithms, the students partially implement some standard algorithms. Afterwards, the students receive a pathophysiological example case with the corresponding input and output data. Based on this data set, which contains too much information, the students select the relevant input and output data and organise it properly. Afterwards, the students study the input and output data by plotting it, making histograms, etc.

Learning goals

- *Implement standard machine learning algorithms;*
- *Analyse and interpret a given set of input and output data that correspond to a given pathophysiological example case.*

P09: Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part II

Description

Based on the example case and corresponding data of part I, the students create a training and test set and apply different machine learning algorithms (e.g. Gaussian process vs. neural network; Gaussian processes with different kernels) to model the relation between the input and output. They compare the model results in terms of goodness of fit and critically interpret the output obtained for new points.

Learning goals

- *Select and implement a proper machine learning algorithm for a pathophysiological example case with given data;*
- *Critically discuss the obtained data-driven model and its output for the test set.*

P10: Development of an in silico trials solution

Description

Based on a general disease description and some general guidelines, the students develop a workflow to create an in silico trials solution. Depending on the interest and perspective of the students, this solution could either use a knowledge-driven or a data-driven model, e.g. by looking up the underlying mechanisms or existing data sets. The students can start working on their developed workflow. The aim is that the students think about the different modeling possibilities and the related assumptions.

Learning goals

- *Identify the different steps required to develop an in silico trial based on a data-driven or knowledge-driven model;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of an in silico trial solution.*

P11: Credibility of predictive models part I

Description

A problem statement is introduced to the student. Based on this information, the students determine a relevant question of interest and context of use. Moreover, they estimate the risk of the solution and they brainstorm on how the subsequent verification and validation steps could be performed. In this respect, the students need to identify the expected sources of errors related to a potential in silico model and its validation and verification.

Learning goals

- *Identify the common sources of errors in the development of in silico models;*
- *Apply the subsequent steps of the credibility workflow, proposed in the ASME V&V40 guidelines related to in silico modeling, to a given example case.*

P12: Credibility of predictive models part II

Description

The students receive a pathophysiological example case together (related to previous exercise session) with the implementation of the corresponding in silico model. They first perform verification of the implementation. Afterwards, they perform a validation of the implementation, by critically considering the modelling assumptions and by comparing the in silico results to the results of a real patient case. The impact of different modelling assumptions on the model output is considered in a sensitivity study. The output distribution also allows the students to gain insight into the output uncertainty.

Learning goals

- *Perform verification of a given pathophysiological in silico example case.*
- *Perform validation of a given pathophysiological in silico example case.*
- *Perform an uncertainty quantification and sensitivity study of a given pathophysiological in silico example case.*